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Application of Multiple Intelligence Theories in Elementary School

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Abstract: Knowledge of the theory of multiple intelligences (MI) is of great importance for teachers, in order to be able to recognize students' affinities, and motivate and guide them in encouraging them. Often, teachers are not familiar with the aforementioned theories or have only mentioned them during their studies. Therefore, if teachers do not know how to recognize them in practice, they cannot help students develop and improve their intelligence. This paper will present teachers' attitudes towards understanding MI, encountering them through education, and obstacles to recognizing them. The respondents were teachers (N=25), and the results were collected via a questionnaire, where the teachers shared their experiences on the aforementioned issue. The results are presented qualitatively using a descriptive method. Although the subjective views of teachers were presented, they will provide insight into an important issue that has rarely been researched in schools in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The shortcoming of this paper is in the small sample of respondents, and certainly leaves room for more recent MI research, with the aim of providing support to students in order to become familiar with and develop in the field of MI.

Keywords: multiple intelligences, stimulating environment, students, teachers, teaching process.

Introduction

Intelligence is often correlated with school success, regardless of whether school success affects intelligence or vice versa. During schooling, increases in IQ have been recorded, which indicates a positive influence of the school environment on the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, perception, classification and language abilities. Through the educational process, the school undoubtedly influences the development of all components of intelligence. Gardner (1983) developed the theory of multiple intelligences in order to expand the concept of understanding intelligence. He was an advocate of a different approach to detecting and classifying children's abilities using different means with a stimulating environment that will encourage the child to express and demonstrate intelligence differently without using conventional tests. Pekdemir, Akyol, (2015), believe that the affinities of students and the development of MI, conditioned by various factors, have a cultural framework, but are dependent on the teacher, his teaching methods, and ways of encouraging students to think innovatively. The teacher should be trained to recognize and apply MI in practice, work with students and encourage them in areas in which they are more successful. A common problem in the educational system is the halting of students in their growth and development, and the lack of understanding for the student. Gardner (1999) lists nine types of intelligence: interpersonal, intrapersonal, natural, bodily-kinetic, visual-spatial, mathematical-logical, linguistic, musical. This paper will point out the importance of teachers' knowledge of multiple intelligences in order to recognize and encourage them in students. Gardner (2008) emphasizes the quality of teachers' teaching as the most important factor for improving students' intelligences. The teacher recognizes students' affinities, ways of thinking and solving problems in the teaching process. The research by (Hu, Yang, 2022), applied a new teaching method in the experimental class, and a traditional method in the second grade, in English language teaching. The application of the new method based on the theory of multiple intelligences proved to be more effective because students showed better reading abilities, but also increased students' interest in reading. The mentioned method gave good results in logical-mathematical and visual-spatial intelligence. This paper will examine teachers' knowledge of multiple intelligence theories and their application.

Methodology

The aim of the research was to examine teachers' opinions on Gardner's MI theory and its practical application in teaching. The research problem is teachers' knowledge of and practical application of MI in the classroom, in the educational system. The research tasks were: to examine teachers' knowledge of MI theories, the application of multiple intelligences and obstacles to their application in the educational system. This research used a qualitative method in which the focus is on the personal experience of the respondents who will express their opinion on MI theories through a subjective presentation. An interview was used where the teachers had the opportunity to connect theory and practice, and describe their experience and application of the aforementioned theories using a descriptive method. The interview contained 8 questions that covered the aforementioned issues and gave the respondents freedom of expression and free expression of their opinions. The interview was previously announced and agreed upon with the school management.

The participants in this qualitative research were teachers (N=25), the youngest respondent was 27 years old, and the oldest was 59 years old. The remaining respondents were aged 31-54. Respondents over 50 completed their studies and further education in the post-war period, so the Theory of Multiple Intelligences was mostly unknown to them. Respondents under 45, who have master's degrees, are mostly familiar with the theory but rarely apply it. Six respondents are mathematics teachers, two are computer science teachers, eight are Croatian language teachers, five are English language teachers and four are biology teachers.

Research results

When asked about their knowledge of Gardner's MI theory, ten respondents over the age of 45 gave similar answers. They were not familiar with the theory during their studies, but later in their work through professional development they heard about it. Honestly, they did not really learn to distinguish and recognize it in their students. These teachers mostly evaluated and assessed their students through their oral and written answers, and through the students' grades they assumed that students with higher grades were more intelligent than students with lower grades. Of the younger teachers, 7 out of 45 were familiar with the theory but did not really use it much in their work. Eight teachers under the age of 32 were well acquainted with MI, having studied and adopted it through several subjects during their studies. In their work, they sometimes assess MI on their students, but due to lack of time and adequate questionnaires, everything stops there.

The second question related to expressing opinions on their knowledge of the MI Theory. Most teachers expressed a similar opinion, as they believe that they are an excellent way to detect student potential, affinities and abilities. They are a path to a quality approach to students where the focus will not be only on assessing students, but on discovering affinities through teaching subjects and motivating students in that direction. They believe that the application of the aforementioned theory at an earlier age would contribute to an easier choice of secondary school and later studies. Of course, a change in legal regulations is primarily needed, specifically the Law on Primary and Secondary Education. The application of this theory in the classroom would help students unleash their creative potential.

The third question about the application of MI, the respondents mostly expressed the opinion that they do not apply it in their work. Respondents younger than 35 are more interested in it, and sometimes apply it. The initiative for applying the aforementioned theories often comes from the school pedagogue, because they have acquired greater theoretical knowledge about this theory during their studies. Younger teachers believe that by organizing debates, workshops and creative methods in teaching, they can meet some criteria for detecting and recording some of the intelligences. Respondents older than 45 complain about their younger colleagues who insist on modern teaching and neglect traditional teaching. Creative teachers, through the application of problem-based and project-based teaching methods, and games as one of the methods, encourage students to express themselves creatively, and thus achieve better results in teaching. However, they all believe that the teacher is an important factor who, through the application of different methods in teaching, contributes to the development of multiple intelligences in students. When asked about the

frequency of application of the MI theory in the classroom, the majority of respondents claimed that they apply it rarely, and only with students who show creative potential and have better academic performance. Judging by this, there is no great desire for teachers to apply it in their teaching, but perhaps also due to insufficient knowledge of the student classification system according to this theory.

When it comes to obstacles to the application of the MI theory, respondents cite various reasons. Eight respondents believe that we have an outdated educational system, teachers who use teaching methods that turn students into passive listeners and recipients of information. Ten respondents also cite students' reduced interest in teaching and unwillingness to cooperate in class as a reason. One third of respondents believe that professional development of teachers on this topic is necessary. Some of the respondents point out the limitations of teachers through legal legislation but also ignorance of the aforementioned theory. A small number of younger respondents believe that this theory is easy to apply to individual students, but it is more difficult to apply to a larger number of students, although it was a subject that these teachers teach.

Discussion

From these responses, it can be concluded that all respondents showed interest in applying the MI Theory. Older respondents were honest about their lack of knowledge of this theory, but they do not deny the benefits of its application in the classroom for better quality student work through improving skills and abilities, and communication skills. Professional development can be useful, but study curricula and programs are key to learning about the theories of multiple intelligences, as well as their practical application in the classroom with students. Armstrong (2006) points out the method of evaluating and assessing student knowledge through numerical assessment as the biggest obstacle to applying Gardner's MI theory in schools. The use of traditional tests and oral knowledge exams stifles the creative potential of students. Sternberg (2012) believes that the application of the MI theory provides many advantages for student progress in accordance with student affinities and creative expression. Research on obstacles to the application of the MI theory, Gurcay, Ferah, (2017) points out the lack of time for implementing MI in classrooms as the main problem. Overburdening students with teaching content, reproductive learning, pressure from final exams and excessive parental expectations are the reasons for the difficult application of the aforementioned theory. Teachers do not have the necessary knowledge about MI, insufficient time and financial resources. Underpayment and constant dissatisfaction of teachers as well as belittling the teaching profession are also reasons that demotivate teachers. The findings of the research by (Zhaowe, Haihong, 2024) point out that students possess different intelligences outside the traditional framework of mathematical and linguistic intelligence. The teacher's engagement and commitment in the classroom is certainly one of the factors of success in the development of the student's given intelligence. These authors point out a stimulating environment as one of the factors, but also interpersonal communication in the classroom. The development of multiple intelligences is culturally conditioned, so an individual and holistic approach to the student is expected. Pekdemir, Akyol, (2016). Walel's research, (2024), shows that despite teachers' knowledge of MI theories, their

application encounters various obstacles. Teachers' knowledge of this theory is limited and difficult to apply in teaching content. Students showed interest in new methods and were more motivated and successful. González-Treviño et al. (2020) state the continuous training of teachers in order to be more successful in the application of MI, by adapting curricula to the intelligence of students. They focus on strengthening the school infrastructure and training teachers to support musical, kinesthetic and visual-spatial intelligence.

Conclusion

The research findings show that teachers are not sufficiently familiar with the theories of multiple intelligences, and if they are familiar with them, they rarely apply them in their work with students. The reasons are multiple, including limited time during the lesson, the inability to leave the given framework of teaching content. Teachers need greater support from principals, professional development in order to improve their theoretical knowledge and practical knowledge of the above. The application of MI theories is constantly faced with the challenges of modern teaching, which is intertwined with traditional methods that are culturally conditioned and often limit students. Therefore, non-cognitive intelligences remain neglected in an education system that mostly relies on standardized tests. Professional development of teachers through the offer of more creative methods and forms of work would certainly benefit the more frequent application of MI in the teaching process. This work certainly leaves room for more extensive research on this issue in order to find innovative ways of learning and teaching with an emphasis on motivating and improving students in all teaching areas.

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